

Debates

On the surface – images of architecture
and public space in debate. Conference proceedings

scopio EDITIONS

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Book of abstracts – On the surface 2012

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Debates collection is the publishing medium for authors who have participated in conferences, debates and roundtables by presenting papers, projects or works considered of interest and significant quality, which promote the critical debate related to Architecture, Arte and Image.

A coleção Debates é o suporte de divulgação de autores que participam em conferências, debates, tertúlias e mesas redondas através de artigos, projectos ou trabalhos considerados de interesse e com qualidade significativa, que de alguma forma promovam uma reflexão alargada em torno da Arquitectura, Arte e Imagem.

Program

14 JUNE 2012 Fernando Távora Auditorium

Pedro Leão Neto e Pedro Bandeira: Opening session

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Philip Ursprung: *Surface Tension: Peter Zumthor and Photography*

Vitor Silva: *Imagens de Arquitectura: contradições de superfície*

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CALL FOR PAPERS

Luis Urbano: *Real Fiction*

Cláudio Reis: *Maquetas*

Alexandra Areia: *Arquitectura "talking head"*

14:30 **ROUND-TABLE #1** – Architecture between Portrait and Landscape (moderated by Pedro Bandeira)

Duarte Belo

Margarida Medeiros

Ana Luísa Rodrigues

Tiago Casanova

ROUND-TABLE #2 – Cityzines and Archizines Live (moderated by Nuno Grande)

Elias Redstone

Joaquim Moreno

Pedro Leão Neto

Ana Aragão

Ivo Poças Martins

OPENING OF THE EXHIBITIONS – FAUP

ARCHIZINES | CITYZINES: Alternative publications on Photography and Architecture

15 JUNE 2012

Marco Iuliano: Lucien Hervé: Architecture as Spatial Sequences

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CALL FOR PAPERS

Mohsen S. Far: *Questioning the Impacts of Still-Image and Photography on Local Urban Culture*

Miguel Silva Graça; Miguel Pinto: *Fotografia e Arquitectura Moderna: a visão de Teófilo Rego e a Nova Monumentalidade de João Andresen*

Luis Lus-Arana: *Dystopia Whenever | Dystopian Thought and the Production of Urban Image*

Ivo Poças Martins: *Mapear a cidade invisível: Porto and the Life Aquatic.*

ROUND-TABLE #3 – The Other Public Space or the Image as Construction of a Space (moderated by Susana Ventura)

Eduardo Brito

Patrícia Almeida

Rita Castro Neves

Andreia Garcia

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José Luís Neves

ROUND-TABLE #4 – ARC+D (moderated by Pedro Leão Neto)

Marco Iuliano

Pedro Rocha

Gonçalo Morgado da Silva

Bruno Moreira

Augusto Sousa

António Coelho

Anselmo Canha

João Castro Ferreira

COMITTEES/ COMITÉS

Commissioner/ Comissariado

Pedro Leão Neto (CCRE/FAUP)

Pedro Bandeira (CCRE/EAUM)

Scientific Committee/ Comissão Científica

André Tavares (FAUP)

Carlos Machado (ATPH/FAUP)

Francisco Ferreira (EAUM)

Gabriela Vaz-Pinheiro (FBAUP)

Joaquim Moreno (CCRE/FAUP)

Marta Cruz (AdC/FAUP)

José M. Rodrigues (DAVD-UE)

Paulo Catrica (EAUM)

Pedro Bandeira (CCRE/EAUM)

Pedro Gadanho (CCRE/FAUP)

Pedro Leão Neto (CCRE/FAUP)

Susana Oliveira (FAUTL)

Teresa Ferreira (PACT/FAUP)

Vitor Silva (FAUP)

Organising Committee/ Comissão Organizativa

Andrea Vieira (CCRE / FAUP)

Bruno Moreira (CCRE / FAUP)

Gonçalo Morgado da Silva (CCRE / FAUP)

Punkto and *Opúsculos* present mainly writings on architecture (the limits of the practice and theory); working within few means, they are simple black and white stapled A4 prints that are distributed freely or can be downloaded and printed by anyone. These can be accurately called fanzines, along with *Friendly Fire*, all of them Porto based projects that aim at a limited number of interested readers. Needless to say, the precarious character of the fanzines is one of its main strengths. *Chocolates Cantantes* was a very particular and limited kind of document made by two local heroes (more than a "zine", a statement), with an explicit ironic bias that questions the media hype of architecture and the role of its celebrities. Some successful examples come from academic groups of students, that direct and print, often with a professional engagement, truly interesting and consistent journals. *Dédalo* (FAUP, Porto) and *Nu* (DARQ, Coimbra) are growing student projects, the later one having printed 38 numbers until now (being also part of the archive Archazines). *Unidade*, a politicized vehicle that served as motto for calling into question the teaching/learning direction of the School, had a very important role in the Faculty of Porto since its first issue in 1988. Illustrations and the manipulation of images, as well as the variety of layouts designed for each article were an important part of the content that swung between the young innocence and the conscious debate of emergent topics. *Laura*, *Joelho* or *In sí(s)tu* come from the teaching sphere of the academic structure and operate as more disciplined (graphical and conceptually) investigation tools. Along with the previous examples, *Index NewsPaper*, *A-Mag* or *scopio magazine* bend to a more "prozine" identity – to use Beatriz Colomina's term –, and are distributed internationally offering a bilingual edition. These publications can be purchased by a wider specialized public, placing emphasis on the format of the object (*Index* resembles a large newspaper and *scopio* has an appealing pocket format). Other disciplinary areas related to architecture also contributed to the comprehensiveness of the exhibition: construction, represented by the specialized magazine *Sebentas de Obra*, or drawing, presented by *Psiax*. *Prototipo*, that had as main theme the space craftsmanship, or *Detritos*, based on an essayist production as a way of speculating about the waste, represented the urban culture. The fact that many publications promote public events or competitions, mostly taking place in the city, reveals the non-autistic posture that could stamp this kind of "geekish" publications. Nonetheless, there is an interest in reaching out for the public, being the situationist-like events promoted by *In sí(s)tu* a good example. Finally, this exhibition constitutes a compliment to the publication as a single object and to the nostalgic idea of collection: owning something that is mine (which I can sign or underline), that I can put on my shelf to be a part of my own library. The library as a metaphor for a life, for architecture, for the labyrinth, as in Borges or in Saramago. The library is the image of an impossible index of the whole world; our small library *Cityzines* is an image of a growing index of the Portuguese printed critique about the city.

Our times, through the eyes of the skull

Ivo Poças Martins, architect, founder and co-editor of *Friendly Fire*

As we state in our presentation text: "*Friendly Fire* is an independent architecture collective interested in subversive and humorous narratives and practices. Its aim is to address the architectural culture and its effects on everyday life in an alternative and informal perspective." We feel that the documentation of the informal discourse around architecture is often neglected and eventually lost. We're interested in gathering the by-products and any leftovers of the architecture production: an untold anecdote behind a project, building mistakes or an unexpected perverse design consequence. Our headquarters, placed in Bouça, a housing complex designed by Siza, one of Porto's Pritzker laureates, is itself a conglomerate of its leftover spaces itself – we occupy a 25sqm office in a single room, meant to serve as a meeting room for the building's dwellers, and a corner shop which was never before occupied due to its small size and odd proportions. The informality of the spaces in which we operate and relate with others influences the tone of our conversations and also of our production. The content of this editorial project is mostly done by the six members of *Friendly Fire* or in straight collaboration with invited authors. In any case, it's always the result of lively talks around the subjects of each issue. Printing in short runs is a way of widening these conversations to our readers, getting to know them and, ultimately, turning each one into an accomplice.

The distribution process is done directly during a launch event or via postal service. The choice of the fanzine format is thus more a communication strategy than a mere nostalgic or aesthetic option (but not much more). Following the tradition of these sorts of publications, or little magazines, the final product has a visual and tactile quality that we expect will contribute to make its content last longer. In order to achieve this, we resort to several gimmicks: *Friendly Fire* is fully designed in AutoCad, each issue is hand-numbered or made unique by some other mean and, finally, it's printed in black and white and manually put together in Fânzeres, our self-dubbed fanzine Mecca.

It may seem an anachronism that little over a decade has passed since the Internet has become an indissociable part of our lives and the subject of the resurgence of the architecture's printed matter is already being discussed, as both *Cityzines* and *Archazines* illustrate so well. In answer to that we use Prince's words: "The internet is like MTV. At one time, MTV was hip, and suddenly it became outdated." In the case of *Friendly Fire*, having one foot firmly in the physical word (although maintaining the tip of the other on the cloud) paid off beyond any of

our initial expectations. We believe we have reached much more people by doing so than if we had chosen an exclusively online strategy. Regardless of our very small budget and number of printed issues, the local character of the addressed subjects and even of the initial choice of writing in Portuguese, it is safe to state that our publication raised almost as much interest abroad as it did in our country. Of course Prince's notion of synchronism isn't consensual, to say the least, as one can tell by his insistence on wearing bell bottoms from the 70's to our days. In 1982, however, he was looking forward when he wrote a song where he said he was going to party as if he was 17 years ahead of his own time. In the second decade of this new century, *Friendly Fire* will follow his steps and keep acting "like it's 1999".

Second Day Presentation

Lucien Hervé: Architecture as Spatial Sequences

Marco Iuliano, University of Liverpool, School of Architecture

In 1987, Peter Zumthor commissioned the Swiss photographer Hans Danuser to portray his chapel Sogn Benedetg in Sumvitg, in the Swiss Alps. The series of atmospheric black and white photographs of the chapel in the fog shaped the image of Zumthor as a romanticist, anti-urban architect. They also forged the image of Swiss Architecture in general. In retrospect, I want to analyze the various levels of meaning, which converge in the architectural photography on Zumthor's early work. Zumthor commissioned Danuser after seeing his critical documentation of the interior of nuclear power plants – controversial, normally invisible spaces. Simultaneously, there was a vivid debate on the protection of the environment in the Alps, a region both dependent on cheap nuclear energy running pumped-storage hydroelectricity and on its natural beauty. Did photography allow a link, perhaps unconscious, between the isolated chapel and the conflicts of the post-industrial society? Did the spatial logic of Zumthor's architecture, its way to deal with surfaces, materialize in the medium of photography before it was articulated on the level of discourse under the label of "topological architecture"? Did the discontinuity of space and time – a core theme of globalized culture – become visible on the plane of photography before it was perceived in architecture and before it could be grasped in theory?